

Errata and addenda for my doctoral thesis, “*Dynamics at the Orbital Ordering Phase Transition in MgV₂O₄ and at the Ferromagnetic Phase Transition in MnSi*”

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1. The usage of the instrument *EIGER* (at Paul Scherrer Institute, Villigen, Switzerland) should also include reference [1], which was not yet available at the time of writing. Similarly, the usage of the instrument *TRISP* (at Maier-Leibnitz-Zentrum, Garching, Germany) should also include the references [2] and [3].
2. Pages 79-81 (“Linewidths”): In the chapter about the MgV₂O₄ phonon linewidths, general references to *TRISP* were given for its software developed by T. Keller (“*SERESCAL*”), which we used for resolution calculation and data treatment. A more specific paper about the algorithm has now become available [4].
3. All formula numbers cited for [5] refer to that book’s accompanying digital version “*Desktop Bronstein*” on CD-ROM, not the paperback version (unfortunately, the formula numbering differs between the two).
4. New results: Section 5.3.4 on pages 82-83, field-dependent results of MgV₂O₄: New, more detailed results could not observe the subtle energy shift of the phonon energies vs. external field, see our ILL experimental report 79659 for proposal 7-02-177 (2020) for more details. The report is available here: <https://doi.org/10.5291/ILL-DATA.7-02-177>.
5. Typo in section 6.4 on page 87 (missing letter underlined): “They [meaning Ref. 96 in the thesis] interpret the observations [...]”
6. Typo in equ. 7.15 on page 96, “Example spin-wave dispersion”: Upper bounds for the sum indices should be N_N and N_{NN} instead of 12 and 8.
7. Chapter 7.3, fig. 7.7 on page 105: The nuclear, non-magnetic structure of MnSi can be found in most MnSi papers, for example [6] or [7].
8. The original website for *Rescal* [8], on whose source code the resolution calculation of our software package *Takin* [9] is originally based (page 139 of the thesis), is not available anymore. Instead a backup of the old site is linked here [8].
9. Typo in appendix A.1.1, page 139, line 3 (correction underlined): “[...] used in all real triple-axis ~~control~~ systems instruments and their control systems [...]”
10. In appendix A.1.1, pages 139-143, which verifies the results of [10] for the crystal matrices and the spectrometer angles:
 - (a) Page 139, equ. A.2: Matrix A should be transposed in addition to being inverted: $B = 2\pi A^{-T}$.
 - (b) Page 143, equ. A.14 misses an arccos before the first term in brackets:
$$\psi_s = -\arccos(\dots) - \arctan(\dots) + \kappa.$$
11. Appendix G.1 (“List of Publications”) on page 185, first point, *Takin* [9] (underlined parts were missing because these appendices were split off the main chapter): “*Reported in ch. 3.8 on pp. 32-25 and appendices A.1, A.2 and A.3 on pp. 137-149.*”
12. All theoretical plots concerning the MnSi chapters were generated using the code from Ref. 54 in the thesis. That reference was forgotten for fig. 8.6 (top left panel) on p. 118 and fig. 8.7 (top left panel) on p. 119 of the thesis.

References

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